

Analytical Studies on Environmental Pollution

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In this paper an outline of the analytical studies on Damodar river water pollution in Durgapur-Asansol industrial belt is presented in the perspective of a critical review of the state of art on environmental pollution. Special emphasis is placed on analytical approach to the subject. More than one hundred important references are listed.

ENVIRONMENTAL pollution has been defined as the unfavourable alteration of our surroundings, partly or largely as an impact of increasing industrialization and related human activities. The continuous growth of industries in this century speeded up greater control of the environment by men on one hand but on other hand, it accelerates pollution of the precious gifts of nature, namely, air, land and water by man.

The concept of environmental pollution is, however, not new¹. Even in the thirties Robert Frost described in his poem "New Hampshire" the concern of the "environmentalist" and sounded a note of warning which is quite relevant even today: "How many times it thundered before Franklin took the hint! How many apples fell on Newton's head before he took the hint! Nature is always hinting at us. It hints over and over again. And suddenly we take the hint".

Indeed, we have started to look at the problem seriously only after the pollutants and poisons in our air, earth and water piled up to the point where they have posed a serious threat to human life. We are now aware that it is a gigantic task to make up within a few years for decades or rather centuries of environmental damage and degradation.

Environmental pollution is not only associated with industrial growth but also with the pressure of population on scarce natural resources. Urbanisation without townplanning is a cause of land pollution. Lack of basic civic amenities such as sanitation, water supply, housing in urban complex lead to problem of waste disposal. The continuous influx of population from rural areas to urban areas has added to this problem. Having polluted the land, we started also to pollute the last clean place on the globe, namely, the seas and oceans on the assumption that the self-cleansing ability of the seas and oceans would somehow solve the problem. The oceanographer, Jacques Cousteau warns us that the floor of the Mediterranean is littered with the debris and waste of modern technology. Ecologists assert that it is a dying sea. The cost of environmental pollution is high relative to socio-economic advantages of increased industrialization. Therefore, it is more than high time that we have to tackle the problem of environmental pollution on an emergency basis.

Classification

Pollution can be classified under three broad headings depending on its nature: A. Air Pollution, B. Water Pollution and C. Pollution due to solid and industrial waste, sewage and sludge, agricultural products etc. The last category actually contributes to the first two categories. Hence we shall restrict our discussion to air and water pollution.

A. Air Pollution²⁻⁴:

Atmospheric pollution is due to the presence of particulate pollutants (e.g. solid particles or liquid suspended in the air causing smoke, mists etc.) and due to gaseous pollutants (e.g. carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide, oxides of nitrogen, hydrocarbons etc.). The air pollution originates from processes such as evaporation, chemical and nuclear reactions, resulting in high concentrations of the contaminants in the air. The gaseous wastes from automobile exhaust and factory chimnies as well as primitive forms of heating (e.g. burning coals, cowdung cakes) are the major sources of air pollution in big cities.

Carbon monoxide: The most harmful of the gaseous contaminants is carbon monoxide resulting from incomplete combustion of carbon. The average world-wide concentration in the atmosphere is 0.1 ppm. It may rise to 30 ppm or more during rush hour traffic in big cities having too many vehicles on the road. The maximum tolerance limit of CO for a healthy worker for an 8 hr-working day is 10 ppm. The toxic action of CO is due to its reaction with haemoglobin in the blood cell which leads to unconsciousness (300 ppm) and ultimately to death (750 ppm of CO).

Sulfur dioxide: Sulfur dioxide is another major air pollutant which is injurious both to animal and plant life and it also contributes to the formation of "Smog". Main sources of SO₂ emission are oil refineries, thermal stations, fertilizer plants, sulfuric acid plants and petroleum industries. The total quantity of annual discharge of SO₂ into the atmosphere is estimated at about 8×10^7 tons. Much of it, however, is ultimately converted into sulphates in the soil. SO₂ causes damage to nucleic acids in several ways. High SO₂ concentrations in the atmosphere lead to major air pollution disaster that occurred earlier in large cities such as London (1911) causing many deaths (London Smog).

Hydrogen Sulphide : Decomposition of organic matter, sewage, petroleum industries, refineries etc. are the main sources of its emission. H_2S may cause respiratory irritations to man and corrosion of materials and it affects the growing tips of sensitive plants.

Nitrogen oxides : Nitrogen oxides are produced in any combustion process occurring in presence of air. Nitric oxide is also formed under electric sparks and is present in the exhaust gases of automobiles, explosive industries and other vehicles. The total quantity of nitrogen oxide discharged annually into the world atmosphere is estimated at 5×10^7 tons which is finally converted into nitrates in the soil. High concentrations of NO_2 may lead to chronic respiratory ailments.

Lead (Pb) : Lead is another major pollutant which originates mainly from exhausts of automobiles which burn fuel having a lead compound, $Pb(C_2H_5)_4$ as an anti-knock additive. It is discharged during combustion in the form of lead chloride and lead bromide along with exhaust gases. About 2×10^5 tons of Pb^{2+} are discharged into the atmosphere annually all over the globe. The upper tolerance limit of Pb^{2+} in the air is 10 mg/m^3 . But in big cities such as Los Angeles the Pb^{2+} concentration may be as high as 54 mg/m^3 . The Pb^{2+} discharged into the atmosphere ultimately contaminates natural surface water and also fields adjacent to the highways. It enters into animal body through food crops. Lead compounds coagulate body proteins and seriously disrupt metabolic processes.

The exhaust emissions from diesel engines, jet engines and artificial satellites have contributed in a large measure to air pollution in recent years.

B. Water Pollution

Water is considered to be polluted when its quantity degenerates due to sewage, industrial water supply and as an environment for aquatic life and aesthetics, is damaged beyond reasonable limits. Pure natural water is colourless, tasteless and odourless containing some dissolved gases and mineral salts in amounts which are harmless for drinking purposes and also beneficial for aquatic life. Some such contaminants may prove to be harmful when their concentration exceeds certain limits (tolerance limits). The tolerance limits for some of the major inorganic pollutants in natural water (other than sea water) are as follows .

CO_3^{2-} , HCO_3^- (upto 150 ppm), dissolved oxygen (<4 ppm), free Cl_2 (upto 0.75 ppm), F^- (upto 1.7 ppm), Cl^- (upto 150 ppm), NO_3^- (upto 45 ppm), NO_2^- (upto 0.1 ppm), PO_4^{3-} (Nil), SO_4^{2-} (upto 250 ppm), SiO_2 (upto 30 ppm), Fe^{3+} (upto 3 ppm), Mn^{2+} (upto .05 ppm), Cr^{3+} (upto .05 ppm), Cu^{2+} (upto 1 ppm), Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Se, As⁵⁺, lead (very low).

Sea water is the most polluted form of natural water having large concentrations (about 3.5%) of dissolved salts. For example, one litre of sea water

contains the following major components (in mole) :

Si 6.06 ; Al^{3+} 1.85 ; Cl_2 0.55 ; Na⁺ 1.23, Ca^{2+} 0.57, Mg^{2+} 0.58, K^+ 0.42, CO_3^{2-} .02, O_2 .03, Fe^{3+} .55, Ti^{4+} .06, SO. 1, F^- .03, PO_4^{3-} .02, Mn^{2+} ,.01, N_2 .10.

Compounds of mercury, lead, cadmium, copper, nickel, zinc etc. which are drained into the sea through river waters from various sources are the utmost concern as toxic pollutants. Mercury is consumed by and accumulates in marine animals. Normal levels of mercury in fish are between .02 to .2 ppm. But this level has been found to increase above 1 ppm. in Japan (Minamata), Sweden and U.S.A., due to discharge of mercury compounds from industrial wastes into the sea. Consumption of such contaminated fish presumably led to well-known incidence of Minamata type of disease (Japan) taking toll of several hundred lives. Mercury discharged in any form (Hg^0 , Hg^{2+} , $C_6H_5Hg^+$, $CH_3O-CH_2-Hg^+$) can be converted to highly toxic methyl mercury, CH_3Hg^+ or dimethyl mercury [$(CH_3)_2Hg$] in aquatic environments through the activity of certain microorganisms as shown in the following Fig. (1)⁶.

Fig. 1. Biochemical transformation of mercury compounds in aquatic environments.

Fig. 2

Fig. 2. Metal dynamics in an environmental segment.

The existence of metal in one form or another in an environmental segment (atmosphere/hydrosphere/lithosphere) is highly dependent on temperature, pH and ionic strength (Fig.2). Conversion of one form into another may be chemically or bio-chemically initiated.

Among various organic pollutants, synthetic insecticides such as DDT deserve special mention. Such insecticides found widespread application since 1940 all over the world for increasing food production by eradicating insect-borne diseases in crops. The concentration of such materials has increased in lakes, rivers and seas. These are not biodegradable and accumulate in fish and from there it goes along the food chain into animals and human beings.

Sewage is another serious source of water pollution. It consists of organic matter as well as inorganic salts like phosphates (mainly from detergents), nitrates, chlorides etc. When the sewage runs into the natural water most of the organic matter undergoes oxidative degradation by the action of bacteria and other microorganisms present in natural water. In this process dissolved oxygen is consumed and if it continues, there may not be enough oxygen into the water to support aquatic lives (fishes and aquatic animals). Too much accumulation of phosphates and nitrates into the neutral water promotes the growth of algae which leads to *algal bloom* on the surface of water which ultimately turns a lake into a swamp and finally into a meadow without any aquatic life beneath the surface of water (*eutrophication of lakes*). Large concentrations of nutrients in water also seriously hamper fishing, navigation, irrigation and production of hydroelectric power.

State of the art in environmental pollution

This section gives a review of the more significant work done during the last five years. Considerable work has been reported on water pollution compared to air pollution and this trend is continuing.

A. Air Pollution

In western countries the governments recognised the increasing problem of air pollution with industrial growth and started enacting laws for enforcing air pollution control measures. In U.S.A., the Clean Air Act was introduced in 1960 and amended from time to time – it provided for evaluation and control of emissions from both mobile and stationary sources.

Nitrogen Oxides from industrial exhausts were removed mainly by two methods: (i) Wet Scrubbing—the scrubbing agents used are KMnO_4 in H_2SO_4 ⁶, aqueous sulphite containing Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ca^{4+} etc.⁷, lime water and H_2O_2 ⁸, ferrous sulphate solution with EDTA⁹, $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4$ in alkali¹⁰, ferrous alum etc.

(ii) (a) By catalytic reduction to nitrogen—Many catalysts are employed for this purpose. A few of them are: mixed oxides containing (Fe_2O_3 , Cr_2O_3 ,

MnO_3)¹², (SnO_3 , V_2O_5)¹³, (NiO , CuO)¹⁴, (V_2O_5 , Cr_2O_3)¹⁵, Al_2O_3 containing noble metals etc.

(b) By catalytic oxidation and subsequent absorption of NO_2 with Na-type faujesite¹⁶ and other suitable absorbents.

Ammonia from waste gases was eliminated generally by oxidation to N_2 in presence of excess oxygen over a catalyst of mixed oxides (Co_2O_3 , CuO ; Al_2O_3 , Mn_2O_3)¹⁷ at a temperature of 500-700°C.

Sulfur dioxide from various industrial exhausts is removed mainly by wet scrubbing using various scrubbing agents such as lime water¹⁸, sodium sulphite¹⁹, magnesium hydroxide, ammonium sulphate solution at pH 3-4²⁰, hydrated calcium silicate²¹, 30-80% H_2SO_4 in presence of peroxy compounds etc.

A mixture of sulfur dioxide and nitrogen oxide is eliminated by catalytic oxidation at high temperature using catalysts consisting of mixed oxides such as V_2O_5 , Co_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 ²² etc. The oxidation product (SO_3) is absorbed on suitable absorbents. Absorbents such as aluminium oxide, Mn-ferrite are also employed for disulfurization.

Hydrogen Sulphide present in waste gases was removed by various absorbents—alkali²³, ethanolamine etc., and also by catalytic oxidation to sulfur using catalyst such as iron-manganese and complexing agent EDTA²⁴; aqueous buffer solution of borax may also be used.

Automobile exhaust from internal combustion engines generally consists of CO, unburned hydrocarbons, nitrogen oxides, lead tetraethyl vapour etc. These are purified by catalytic oxidation at about 500°C using catalysts such as Pt-Pd-Re-Mg, MnO_2 - SiO_2 ²⁵ etc. These catalysts are generally packed into a converter in the internal combustion engines.

B. Water Pollution

Historically, almost five hundred years ago the United Kingdom was the first country to be seized with the problem of water pollution of the river Thames during the reign of Henry VII. The pollution protection of the Thames was provided for by statute. The River Pollution Prevention Act was enacted in 1876, followed by a series of Acts upto 1936 covering the regulation of industrial waste waters.

A large number of Environmental Protection Agencies (EPA) have been set up in different countries all over the world. In U.S.A., EPA was established in 1970. This looks after all aspects of pollution, waste management, radiation and noise. In India the Government has established National Environmental Planning and Coordination Committee (NEPCC) in 1972. It is entrusted with the task of improving human environment. It also reviews policies on preserving purity of environment, promoting research in environmental

problem etc. The National Environmental Engineering Research Institute (NEERI) at Nagpur is engaged in work on environmental pollution.

The first international conference on water pollution research was held in London in 1962 bringing together research workers in pollution prevention studies from different parts of the world. The conference discussed methods of purifying waste waters with special regard to efficiency and economics and also pollution effects of waste water on natural waters, estuaries and coastal areas. Since then international conference meets every two years in different parts of the world.

Major work on water pollution is centered on removal of contaminants (inorganic and organic) from polluted water (waste water) of industrial effluents discharged into the natural water sources. Ion-exchange method has been extensively employed for such waste treatment. Literature survey shows major contribution to this field by Japanese and Russian Scientists.

Cyanide : Bekenn²⁶ reviewed methods for disposal of cyanide from effluent streams in plating and other metal processing factories. Anion exchange resins were employed for adsorption of cyanide from waste liquors of plating and other industries. The resins were regenerated by treatment with 1N HCl followed by 1N NaOH solution²⁷. Mixed ion exchanger bed consisting of cation exchanger KU-2-8 and anion exchanger AV-17-8 was used for purification of cyanide wastes²⁸. Selective removal of cyanide from industrial waste effluent was carried out by conversion of cyanide to ferrocyanide on treatment with FeSO_4 at pH 8-11 and then adsorption on a weak anion exchanger Amberlite XE-275²⁹.

Phosphate : Phosphate present in industrial waste liquors was removed by adsorption on cation exchanger in Fe(III) form. Capacity upto 9.5 mg. phosphorus per ml. of wet resin was reported³⁰. Red mud (Fe_2O_3) ignited at 800°C was used as an effective adsorbent of phosphorus from waste water at pH 5-7 and also pH 12³¹⁻³². Activated alumina was also used in removal of phosphate from sewage³².

Arsenic : Arsenic present in waste liquors of industries was removed by aerial oxidation in presence of catalyst (MnO_2)³⁴, by co-precipitation with $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ at pH 4.5-9³⁵, by $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ and lime water at pH 10-12³⁶, adsorption on anion exchange resins after oxidation to arsenate³⁷.

Ammonium Ion : Ammonium ions from waste water were removed and recovered by adsorption on various cation exchanger. Some of them are : Diaion PK-228³⁸, Zeolite³⁹⁻⁴⁰, Zerolit - 225⁴¹. An ion-selective zeolite Clinoptilolite⁴²⁻⁴³ is found to be most effective in separating ammonium ion from waste waters.

Chromium : Chromium was removed from plating wastes and also from various industrial effluents by anion exchangers⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸ (AV-17-8, AV-171, Dianion SK IB etc.), cation exchangers⁴⁹⁻⁵⁰ (KU-2x8 Diaion-CR-10

and by mixed cation and anion exchangers⁵¹⁻⁵⁵ [(KU-2, AB-17) (KU-2x8, AV-17x8)] by co-precipitation⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸ of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ with ferric hydroxide after reduction of the hexavalent chromium to trivalent chromium.

Copper, Zinc and Mercury : Copper was removed from electroplating waste solutions by electroanalysis using ion-exchange membrane⁵⁹ and also by continuous counter-current ion exchange process (Amberlite IR-120)⁶⁰.

Zinc was removed from various waste waters by passage through suitable cation exchangers⁶¹⁻⁶⁴ (KU-2x8 in H form, KB-4x10 in Na-form, KB-UP-2-Na⁺ MK-3, xenonit x-SD and Wofatit KPS).

Mercury was removed from industrial wastes by adsorption of its anionic chlorocomplex⁶⁵⁻⁶⁶ or iodide complex⁶⁷ by suitable anion exchanger⁶⁸ (AV-17), chelating resin such as dithizone type (Lewatit M 500⁶⁹ and M 504), fibrous resin of type Mtylon-T at pH-10⁷⁰. High molecular weight amines (Quaternary amines)⁷¹ were successfully used for solvent extraction of mercury from brine solution and other chloride systems. Activated carbon⁷² was also employed for removal of mercury from waste waters.

Phenol : Phenol was removed from various wastes including acid sludge of coke oven plant by adsorption on lignius⁷³, cation exchangers : Sindex CH-20⁷⁴ Amberlite X AO⁷⁵ adsorbent etc.

Analytical approach to Air Pollution Control⁷⁶ :

Since 1955 a large number of laboratory analytical techniques were developed for monitoring and measurements of air pollutants (10-1000 mg/m³). By the mid-1960's gas chromatographic technique became popular as monitoring equipment. A new generation of instruments was gradually developed possessing great sensitivity and selectivity and operated on physical principles rather than wet chemistry.

(a) Atmospheric gases & vapours .

The gas chromatographic technique⁷⁷ has been developed into convenient monitoring equipment for analysis of carbon monoxide, methane and other gaseous hydrocarbons. Gas chromatographs with flame ionisation detectors have been utilized in mobile laboratories for analysis of 30-60 different aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons.

Sulfur dioxide, hydrogen sulphide and other sulfur compounds are measured by flame photometry⁷⁸⁻⁷⁹. Sulphur dioxide is also determined by the collection of the sample in impingers containing hydrogen peroxides. The sulfur dioxide is oxidised to sulphate and analyzed after reaction with barium-chloroanilate colorimetrically at 530 nm. Cationic interferences are eliminated by pretreatment of a solution by cationic exchange resin⁸⁰.

The most efficient method for analysis of nitric oxide in ambient atmosphere involves the use of chemiluminescence emission⁸¹ from the electronic transition $\text{NO}_2^* \rightarrow \text{NO}_2 + h\nu$ produced in the reaction of nitric oxide with ozone (chemiluminescence peak at 1.2 nm.). This method can be used for determination of nitric oxide concentration in the range 0.004 upto 10,000 ppm.

(b) Atmospheric Particulates :

Analysis of gaseous air pollutants is much easier than particulate matter analysis. Particulates larger than $10 \mu\text{m}$ settle readily and are usually associated with dust and dirt. Particulates of such size are deposited in the respiratory tract and cause irritations having toxicological action. Particles between $0.1-10 \mu\text{m}$ are of greatest concern for air pollution and have more toxic effect on our physiological systems.

The electron microprobe has been employed for identification and estimation of a variety of elements including Al, Si, P, S, Cl, K, Ca, V, Fe, Cu, Zn and Pb in air-borne particles. X-ray fluorescence technique is particularly useful for on-site analysis of hazardous elements including Be, Hg, As, Cd, V and Mn.

Particulate matter samples are usually analyzed for the elements after collection on a filter, usually glass fibre or polystyrene membrane filter.

Atomic absorption spectrophotometry⁸²⁻⁸³ is a very sensitive technique for the elements As, Be, Na, K, Ca, Mg, Ba, Cd, V, Co, Cu, Zn, Ag, Ni and Pb.

Thermal neutron activation analysis⁸⁴⁻⁸⁵ has recently found application for determination of Al, V, Mn, Na, Cl and Br in air-borne particulate samples.

Among organic particulates, polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons, particularly α -benzopyrene, have received major attention. Thin layer chromatography has been employed as separation technique and analysis performed by spectrophotometry or spectrofluorometry⁸⁶.

Lead content of automobile exhaust can be determined polarographically on each of a series of particle sized fractions from auto-exhaust. Lead, nitrate, sulphate & chloride in auto exhaust have been analysed by Atomic Absorption and by Nephelometric Methods for the anions⁸⁷.

Diesel exhaust emissions consist of varying concentrations of hydrocarbon. low molecular wt. cracked hydrocarbons as well as partially oxygenated organic products, polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbon, nitrogen oxides etc. Gas chromatography, mass spectrometry, fluorescence spectroscopy are used to identify and measure these compounds (cited in ref. 73).

Analytical approach to Water Pollution Control :

Analytical procedures for measurement of water pollution are classified according to i) the purpose of

analysis (Bio-degradability and toxicity test), ii) nature of the constituent under test (gases, alkalimetals and heavy metals) and iii) the nature of the analytical procedure itself (titrimetry, gravimetry & electrometry).

Analysis for Metals :

In polluted water, metal analysis is generally concerned with (a) alkaline earths (Ca & Mg), (b) iron and manganese, and (c) trace metals [Cu, Cd, Hg, Pb, Zn, As, Cr, Ni, Mo ($10^{-8}M$ to $10^{-10}M$)]. The most intricate problem is concerned with the species characterization at the concentration levels present in the aquatic environment, particularly for trace metals.

Concentration and Separation technique :

Ion-exchange chromatography is a very effective method for concentration and separation of ions from natural and waste waters. The ions are first concentrated on a suitable ion-exchange column and selectively eluted for subsequent determination by appropriate method. In recent years ion exchange membranes have been used instead of ion-exchange columns for separation and concentration of metal ions prior to analysis. A cation exchange membrane can be mounted on the surface of an indicator electrode (usually carbon, platinum or gold) in a voltammetric system. Here the membrane serves as an ion-exchange preconcentration matrix. The major difficulty inherent in cation exchange membrane for transition and heavy metals in natural waters and waste waters is the lack of specificity since most metals are found in the form of inorganic and organic complexes.

Solvent extraction is extensively used for separation purposes. A large number of useful methods are available for the separation of metal ions by successive extractions employing different complexing agents and organic solvents e.g. dithizone, oxine, cupferron, diethyl dithiocarbamate etc.

The analytical techniques should satisfy the following requirements : (i) high sensitivity, (ii) high selectivity, (iii) ability to characterize free and complexed metallic species, (iv) *insitu* measurements, (v) portability and ruggedness for field operations and (vi) suitability for continuous monitoring purposes.

Atomic absorbance and Atomic fluorescence Spectro photometry :

Among the optical methods atomic absorption and atomic fluorescence spectrometry are popular techniques for metal analysis in natural and waste waters. These are highly sensitive (10^{-6} - 10^{-8} mole/lit.) techniques and also have the advantage of specificity. Over sixty elements can be measured easily by AAS in ppm range. Microgram quantities of Co, Cu, Fe, Pb, Ni, Zn have been determined in saline water by extraction of metal complexes with ammonium pyrrolidine dithiocarbamate into methyl isobutyl ketone⁸⁸.

Polarography :

Cu, Bi, Pb, Cd & Zn are measured in the range 0.01 mg/lit. after preliminary extraction with dithizone and carbon tetrachloride. Traces of Cu, Pb, Zn and Mn have been determined at 0.05 mg/ml level in natural waters by oscillographic polarography⁸⁻⁹⁻¹⁰.

Anodic Stripping Voltammetry :

This is one of the most useful electrochemical techniques for trace metal analysis. It involves two consecutive steps : (i) electrolytic separation and concentration of electroactive species to form a deposit for an amalgam on the working electrode and (ii) dissolution (stripping) of the deposit. Quantitative determinations are performed by integrating current-time curves (coulometry at controlled potential) or by measurement of peak current. The technique has been applied for metal analysis in sea water, natural waters, waste waters & drinking water supplies¹¹⁻¹³.

Potentiometric Techniques :

Recently ion selective electrodes have been found to be extremely useful for measurements of a number of metals in natural and waste waters. Electrodes are available for measurement of Co, Mg, Cu, Cd & Pb¹⁴ in the range 10^{-5} to 10^{-8} molar. They are also applicable to measurement of heavy metals in certain industrial waste effluents from plating industries, pickling waste of steel plants.

Analysis of Organic Matters :

Several separation techniques are available for isolation and concentration of organic matters in natural and waste waters. They are generally distillation, solvent extraction, precipitation, crystallization, adsorption, gas chromatography, paper chromatography and thin layer chromatography¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

Adsorption chromatography with activated carbon has been frequently used for separating organic compounds from surface waters and industrial effluents. Paper chromatography and Thin layer chromatography have also been employed for separation and identification of organic constituents in waste waters, phenols, cresols, xylenols and other industrial phenols have been determined by paper chromatography¹⁸. Chlorinated hydrocarbon pesticides have been determined at concentrations of 2 μ g or less¹⁹.

Elemental Analysis :

A gross estimate of organic matter in wastes can be made by measuring total organic carbon (TOC) and in some cases total organic nitrogen (TON) or total organic phosphorus (TOP).

The TOC test determines the total soluble carbon within a few minutes and the method requires less than 0.5 ml of sample²⁰. The aqueous sample can be injected directly into a combustion tube heated to 970°C in a constant stream of oxygen. The organic matter can also be subjected to dry combustion in presence of

a catalyst (CuO, Co₂O₃, etc.) at a temperature of 900-1000°C.

Organic nitrogen is usually determined by Kjeldahl method. In case of organic-bound nitrogen which is not easily transformed to ammonia²¹, mercury is used as a catalyst for digestion.

Organic phosphorus is estimated as usual by wet combustion in sulphuric and nitric acid mixture followed by gravimetric determination as ammonium phosphomolybdate or by colorimetric methods.

The analysis of organic constituent in natural and waste waters is a difficult task, the complication being due to biochemical degradation or chemical transformation of the organic compounds resulting from bacterial action, temperature effect, surface catalysis etc.

Identification :

Spectrometric techniques—IR-UV, Mass spectroscopy and NMR—are useful for the identification of organic compounds in natural and waste waters.

Non-Specific Analysis of Organic Matter is generally based on measurements of quantities of oxidizable organic material either by biologically-mediated oxidation or by chemical oxidation. The most common method for measurement of the susceptibility of a waste to biological oxidation is the biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) test while the chemical oxygen demand (COD) test is useful for measurement of concentration of organic matter oxidizable by a dichromate reflux method. Basically the BOD test is a bioassay procedure for determining the amount of biologically oxidized organic matter in terms of the amount of oxygen consumed²²⁻²⁴.

Studies on Damodar River Water Pollution in Durgapur-Asansol Industrial belt.

In the 45 Km. stretch of industrial belt between Durgapur and Asansol there are as many as 20 industries (heavy & small) in the public and private sectors. The following table gives a list of the major industries which have major share in pollution problem of Damodar River.

Name of Industry	Nature of Effluent
1. Durgapur Steel Plant (D.S.P.), Durgapur.	Suspended solid (coal dust), phenol, cyanide, fly-ash etc.
2. Alloy Steel Plant (A.S.P.), Durgapur.	Dissolved iron scales, acids (pickling liquors), oils & grease.
3. Durgapur Project Ltd. (D.P.L.), Durgapur.	Ammoniacal Spent Liquor (ammonia, thiocyanate, phenol, cyanide etc.)
4. Durgapur Chemicals Ltd. (D.C.L.), Durgapur.	Phthalic acid, Maleic acid, phenols, caustic alkali, chlorine etc.
5. Phillips Carbon Black, Durgapur.	Suspended carbon particles, oils & grease.

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| 6. Durgapur Thermal Power Station (D.T.P.S.), Durgapur. | Ash. | 5. K.H. MANCY, "Analytical Problems on Water Pollution Control" in Analytical Chemistry : Key to Progress on National Problems, NBS Special Publication 351, 1972, p. 297. |
| 7. Fertilizer Corporation of India Ltd. (F.C.I.), Durgapur. | Ammonia, Arsenic. Chromium. | 6. S. TORIUMI, <i>Japan Kokai</i> , 1974, 74, 106, 469; <i>Chem. Abs.</i> , 1975, 83(2), 32550 j. |
| 8. Bengal Paper Mill, Raniganj. | Lignin, Mercaptans, Wood Fibres, Lime sludge, Sulphite, Disulphides, Sulphates, Caustic alkali etc. | 7. M. TAKABATAKE and H. TARUI, <i>Japan Kokai</i> , 1974, 74, 130, 363; <i>Chem. Abs.</i> , 1975, 83(3), 47651 S. |
| 9. Rectit Coleman of India Ltd. Asansol. | Sodium Sulphate (low conc). | 8. Y. NIIMI, S. INENAGE and Y. KUSUMOTO, <i>Japan Kokai</i> , 1974, 74, 128, 867; <i>Chem. Abs.</i> , 1975, 83(3), 47653 U. |
| 10. M/S. Carew & Co, | Suspended solid, potash, phosphorous, nitrogen & dissolved organic matters. | 9. M. SAITO, Y. EGUCHI and M. SANO, <i>Japan Kokai</i> , 1974, 74 128, 888; <i>Chem. Abs.</i> , 1975, 83(7), 120337 a. |
| 11. IISCO, Burnpur. | Waste pickling liquors, spent ammoniacal liquor with high conc. of phenol, lime etc. | 10. T. SAITO, H. TAKAGI and K. WASHIO, <i>Japan Kokai</i> , 1974, 74 126, 585; <i>Chem. Abs.</i> , 1975, 83(7), 120340W. |

In November, 1974 an abnormal situation of water pollution had developed in the Damodar River affecting the industrial and domestic water supply system in Durgapur-Asansol region. The district administration set up an investigation committee to study and report on water pollution of Damodar.

In this laboratory investigations are in progress on pollution status survey of Damodar River stretch in the Durgapur-Asansol industrial belt. Hydrological data of Damodar River basin in the said belt will serve as the background line for overall pollution of the river. Water samples from various survey points from river and also from adjacent wells, where available, are collected to assess the quality of river water and compared with that of ground water. Qualitative tests for both inorganic and organic pollutants are performed by spot tests by standard method. Quantitative estimation of metals and organic pollutants in the river water and ground water is carried out by sensitive trace analysis methods such as extraction spectrophotometry, extraction flame photometry, tracer techniques etc. Separation of the pollutants, both inorganic and organic, is achieved using suitable organic and inorganic ion-exchangers under optimum conditions.

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